

DIDACTIC FOUNDATIONS OF USING ENGLISH MEDIA TEXTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the importance of mass media texts in teaching foreign languages, the concepts of media education, media competence and media text, their differences, and the research of these concepts. Also, important features of mass media texts, their tasks and levels were studied and analyzed.*

Keywords: *text, media text, context, literacy, mass communication, medianess, mass, integrative, audiovisual, audio materials, videos, video-media texts.*

It is an indisputable fact that the use of mass media texts in foreign language practical training in modern universities is effective. In addition, media texts are taking the main place in foreign language teaching, replacing academic texts, and are increasingly used by teachers in language teaching.

“We can safely say that media texts have become an integral part of foreign language teaching: they are used as authentic material during the lesson, they are printed in the form of self-study manuals, they are modeled, they always provide information about the country where the language is being studied”. The use of mass media materials selected by the teacher for learning a foreign language in High education institutions are not a novelty in the methodology of foreign language teaching. So far, articles from foreign newspapers and magazines have been used in this methodology. Recently, however, radio and television programs as well as texts from the Internet have been added to press materials.

Working with such materials in the auditorium gives the teacher great opportunities in solving many methodological tasks:

- to expand students' vocabulary and develop the most common methods in modern grammar structures;
- development and improvement of reading, listening and audiovisual skills, oral monologues and conversational speeches, written speech;
- to develop the skills of conducting conversations on interesting topics;
- getting new information about linguistics and country studies;
- getting new information about intercultural events;
- development of intercultural communication skills.

By introducing foreign media texts into the educational process, the teacher can overcome a number of specific methodological problems, enrich vocabulary, further improve the level of interest and motivation of students, and help them to learn English later.

It should be noted that the language policy of our Republic and the European Union consider that the learning of foreign languages from educational institutions of modern society requires not only the formation of communicative and intercultural competences, but also requires consistent formation, creating a professional and socially competent, mobile person who is able to make sound professional and social decisions. and took responsibility for it.

The use of mass media texts in the educational process helps to develop not only the above-mentioned skills, but also individual characteristics and skills: communication; communication and cooperation skills; the ability to participate as an active subject of social activity; ability to think critically and make independent decisions; ability to work with information; ability to identify and solve problems; ability to adapt to changing life conditions; the ability of self-development and self-discipline; availability of research and creative skills; goodwill; good care; the ability to find compromise solutions; patience and the ability to control oneself in the situation of “communicative failure”.

For our research, some report materials of the BBC1 channel were interested in being used as a methodical guide for senior students of a higher education institution. We believe that it is necessary to single out a number of advantages for using this type of media texts as educational materials in higher education courses.

Below is a feature of English TV news material T. Based on the research of Dobrosklonskaya.

First, the TV news program of the language of the country being studied reflects the real process of events happening in all areas of the native language speakers, which undoubtedly arouses interest in the culture of the students of the English language and the people of the foreign language country.

The presence of interest usually leads to increased student motivation, which is an important factor in the overall learning process. Getting into the social context of all the events happening in the country, analyzing the behavior of local speakers in situations of specific social significance, as well as allows for a better understanding of national characteristics and comparison of cultural realities in different countries, which helps to build intercultural competence among students.

Second, TV news texts appear on three interrelated levels: video sequence, music tracks, and actual spoken text. In English language teaching methodology, if audio materials are provided with video clips, language learning will be more effective. In addition, the music video along with the soundtrack creates the illusion of being in a foreign country.

Thirdly, the structure of the text part of the news is not primary. In addition to the introductory speech, it may include messages from reporters, direct conversations with the reporter, and interviewers. In addition, the text of the message is written by native speakers without errors and voiced by them. All this shows that news texts are important for students in all aspects (phonetic, grammatical, lexical, textual).

The fourth characteristic is this: the language of news texts is enriched with words that represent the realities of the country being studied, as well as words related to culture. Facts help students gain historical information and also provide information about the culture of the country of the language being studied. Colloquial language, which conveys culturally relevant information, is important for understanding the ideology of speakers of a foreign language, their cultural values, as well as attitudes towards other peoples and events in other countries. Analysis of the selection of information in the TV program, despite the duty to present this information and the constant desire of the presenters and commentators to present the news text more meaningfully, helps to better understand the ideological and political views of the listeners regarding the events in other countries.

The fifth characteristic feature of news texts as educational programs is their stability at all levels: format, content, language level. The organized and stable structure of the message text

helps to understand the content and, accordingly, to understand the content. Dividing the news text into thematic blocks allows the teacher to select a list of words and phrases related to the topic and use them as lexical material. The presence of many phrases with repeated verbs, passives and other grammatical structures from program to program allows them to be separated into potentially easy-to-remember parts. Continuing to work with these lexical and grammatical materials will lead to the use of these modern vocabulary and the most common grammatical structures in the students' speech.

The main type of speech activity corresponding to the method of using video-media texts for the purpose of forming cultural competence is listening and audio visualization as part of listening. It should be noted that listening and audiovisual differ from each other in the following ways:

Through the channels of sensory reception: the listening process is received through the auditory channels, the channels of information reception in the audiovisual process are hearing and vision;

Possibilities of filling the audio text with other communicative elements in addition to the background sound; for example, in audio-visualization, audio texts can be combined with various information - visual, image-schematic, text;

3) on different types of materials.

From the above we conclude that; audiovisual is the ability to listen and see at the same time. Audio visualization occurs when a person watches television material, including news.

Thus, English-language video media texts are important for building communicative and intercultural competences.

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